

MULTIMEDIA INSTRUCTION IN TEACHING GRADE 10 MATHEMATICS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY USING MULTIPLE SERIES DESIGN

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Multimedia Instruction in Teaching Grade 10 Mathematics: A Comparative Study Using Multiple Series Design

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Abstract

This study availed particularly the Comparison Research with multiple series design. Two groups were used in the study. One group was the experimental and the other was the control group. The selection as to what group the subjects belong was through drawing of lots. The experimental group consisting of 30 learners was taught daily using the Multimedia Instruction as Strategy. An initial test was conducted before the experiment. The test was adopted and modified from the K-12 Grade 10 Mathematics teacher's guide with table of specification. The control group consisted of 30 learners were taught using the lecture method. The Post Hoc Analysis showed that (i) there is a significant difference between Test 1 and Test 2, (ii) there is a significant difference between Test1 and Test 3, and also (iii) there is a significant difference between Test 2 and Test 3 of the experimental group. This implies that there is always an increase of test scores in every pair and that teaching with the use of multimedia is effective. The result of the Factorial Analysis showed that there is a significant difference in the test scores of the control group and experimental group (Sample A).

Keywords: *multimedia instruction, teaching, multiple series design*

Introduction

David Warlick (2012) quoted, "we need technology in every classroom, students, and teachers' hand because it serves as the pen and paper of our time, and it is the lens through which we experience much of our world," The computer has the potential to provide an opportunity to both "high-tech" experiences for students in Math solving permutations and combinations. This study intends to investigate whether it is worthwhile to integrate multimedia inspired into the teaching and learning process in order to bridge the instructional and knowledge gap. Based from the statement of Deliyannis (2002), potent upshot of multimedia inspired teaching involves the combination of several scientific, research and creative fields which gives a big impact on the interaction process.

Jamieson-Procter (2013) pointed out that Integration of Multimedia Inspired Teaching should be utilized and incorporates into daily teaching learning process. In connection to preparing the learners to the current digital era which closely relates to the utilization of learning technologies in school, due to the fact that the learners are familiar with technology and learn better with creative output produces effective result to the acquisition of learning. The great challenge nowadays as Marzano (2007) stressed, is how to reach generation that listen with its eyes and thinks with its feeling. This is both morally weighty and technologically preconditioned. If technology speed up the space of almost everything, and that the learning process is in and of itself is lifelong, then teachers must find a way to convey his lessons and calibrate the minds for a change.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance of the control group and experimental group before the conduct of the study?
2. Is there a significant difference in the initial test scores of the control group and experimental group?
3. Is there a significant difference in the series of test scores of the control group?
4. Is there a significant difference in the series of test scores of the experimental group? Is there a significant difference in the series of test scores of the control group and the experimental group.

Literature Review

In teaching Math, Warren Moosely (2011), gave reason on multimedia inspired teaching in the classroom. Multimedia gives students a real sense of the abstract things going on and allows them to relate the things they see happening in a practical or a demonstration. Multimedia shows the massive scale of such operations, and will broaden their thinking about how the real world works. Animation can do much better by highlighting key features, or describing changes as students see them happen. With a DVD, there is much more opportunity to include historical film and photos.

In this series, the images help learners to understand that grew out of nineteenth century discoveries. By using video they are particularly helping the visual learners, learners who can understand things better through images, diagrams, animations and seeing things actually happening. The integration of information communication technology (ICT) makes the teacher holds the attention of the learners to have an interactive discussion, engaging activities and make lesser burden to teacher in delivering the lesson interesting, exciting and enjoyable. (Arnseth&Hatlevik, 2012). The main goal of ICT is to make learners think systematically and scientifically, for it offers a far better learning acquisition in getting the information fast, easy and convenient. (Albirini, 2006, p.6)

In the context of teaching Mathematics, multimedia has proven to be an effective tool in enhancing student understanding and engagement. Warren Moosely (2011) highlights the significance of multimedia-inspired teaching by emphasizing that it allows students to connect abstract mathematical concepts to real-world applications. The visual and interactive nature of multimedia provides a deeper understanding of complex operations, which can often seem distant or difficult to grasp in traditional classroom settings. By using animations, multimedia resources can effectively highlight key features and describe dynamic changes, allowing students to see processes unfold in real time.

This study is grounded in the increasing recognition of multimedia's potential to enhance the learning experience in mathematics education. Traditional methods of teaching, while effective to a degree, often fail to engage students in the dynamic and abstract nature of mathematical concepts, especially in subjects such as statistics and probability. Multimedia tools, including platforms like Khan Academy (Khan, 2012), Quizlet (Farley & Moore, 2011), Socrative (Socrative, 2016), and Bamboozle (Puentedura, 2013), offer innovative ways to bridge this gap by incorporating visual, auditory, and interactive elements into lessons, which can help make abstract concepts more accessible and engaging for students.

Research suggests that multimedia can facilitate better understanding by providing multiple representations of content, thus catering to diverse learning styles (Mayer, 2009; Clark & Mayer, 2016). For instance, Khan Academy uses videos to break down complex topics into manageable, easy-to-understand segments, while Quizlet provides interactive flashcards that help students memorize key terms and concepts. Similarly, Socrative allows for real-time formative assessments, enabling teachers to gauge student understanding and provide immediate feedback, while Bamboozle uses game-based learning to create a more interactive and enjoyable learning environment. These tools can increase student engagement by promoting active participation, which is crucial for the mastery of challenging subjects like mathematics (Johnson & Johnson, 2014).

Despite the growing use of these multimedia platforms, there is limited research on their comparative effectiveness in teaching mathematics, particularly in subjects that students often find challenging, such as statistics and probability. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the impact of multimedia-based teaching tools on students' learning outcomes in mathematics, compared to traditional lecture-based instruction. By examining the role of multimedia in fostering student engagement, enhancing retention, and improving performance, the study will contribute valuable insights into the effectiveness of these tools in the classroom (Mayer, 2009; Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001).

There is a growing emphasis on incorporating technology into education, particularly in response to the increasing role of digital tools in students' lives. As digital literacy becomes a crucial component of education, it is essential to investigate how multimedia platforms can not only support academic achievement but also equip students with the skills necessary to thrive in a technology-driven world (Huang & Hew, 2018). This research will help educators better understand the potential of multimedia tools in enhancing learning outcomes, fostering student motivation, and promoting long-term retention, providing a foundation for their broader adoption in mathematics instruction.

Research supports Moosely's view, as studies have shown that multimedia can significantly aid in making abstract concepts more tangible for students. For instance, animations and simulations can illustrate mathematical concepts in ways that are more engaging and easier to comprehend compared to static diagrams or verbal explanations alone (Mayer, 2009). Multimedia tools such as DVDs and digital archives offer additional opportunities to integrate historical films, photos, and other relevant content, which can provide students with a broader context and deepen their understanding of the subject (Moreno & Mayer, 2007).

Multimedia can cater to various learning styles by combining visual, auditory, and kinesthetic elements into a single learning experience, thus increasing engagement and retention (Fleming & Mills, 1992). By incorporating multimedia into the classroom, educators can enhance both the teaching and learning process, making Mathematics not only more accessible but also more enjoyable for students.

Expanding on the role of multimedia in teaching mathematics, Moosely (2011) further discusses how multimedia not only enhances student engagement but also provides diverse learning experiences that address various cognitive processes. One of the key advantages of multimedia is its ability to represent abstract mathematical concepts in a more visual and tangible manner. By incorporating visual aids such as animations, videos, and simulations, students are able to better understand the complexity of mathematical operations and their real-world applications. For instance, in topics such as geometry or calculus, animations allow students to visualize transformations, graph behaviors, and dynamic changes over time, offering insights that would otherwise be difficult to convey through traditional methods.

Research has also shown that multimedia can promote deeper learning by making abstract concepts more concrete. According to Clark and Mayer (2011), multimedia can foster better retention and understanding by engaging multiple senses and facilitating cognitive processing. When students interact with visual representations of math concepts, they can build mental models that help them grasp complex ideas more effectively. When multimedia is used in combination with interactive tools, it encourages active learning, where students can manipulate variables and experiment with different scenarios to see how mathematical principles apply to real-life situations (Zhang, 2011).

Multimedia can also serve to reinforce the relevance of mathematics by connecting the subject matter to real-world contexts. By

presenting mathematical problems through videos, simulations, and interactive platforms, students can see how math is applied in various fields such as engineering, economics, and science. This not only increases student motivation but also shows the practical value of mathematics beyond the classroom. As Moosely (2011) mentions, multimedia can give students a broader perspective on how mathematical operations function at a large scale, enhancing their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Multimedia learning environments foster collaboration and discussion among students. In classrooms where multimedia tools are integrated, students are encouraged to work together to explore and solve problems, share insights, and discuss their understanding of mathematical concepts. This collaborative learning approach not only reinforces the material but also encourages peer teaching, where students explain concepts to one another, thereby solidifying their own understanding (Jonassen, 2000).

The research gap in the context of multimedia-inspired teaching in mathematics, particularly with tools like Khan Academy, Quizlet, Socrative, PPT, Video clips with animations, and Bamboozle, and other multimedia inspired tools, lies in the limited exploration of how these specific multimedia platforms impact student learning outcomes in various mathematical subfields, such as algebra, calculus, or statistics. While platforms like Khan Academy (Khan, 2012), Quizlet (Farley & Moore, 2011), Socrative (Socrative, 2016), and Bamboozle (Puentedura, 2013) have gained traction for their ability to support learning through interactive videos, quizzes, and games, there is still a need for comprehensive studies investigating their direct impact on different mathematical topics and their comparative effectiveness against other multimedia resources or traditional teaching methods. Although some studies have highlighted the benefits of multimedia for teaching abstract concepts (Moosely, 2011; Mayer, 2009), there is insufficient research on how tools like Quizlet's flashcards, Socrative's assessments, and Bamboozle's game-based learning contribute specifically to students' performance, engagement, and retention in mathematics.

While many studies report immediate improvements in student learning outcomes, there is limited research on how students retain and apply their knowledge over time and whether these platforms lead to sustained learning progress (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). Additionally, research on the extent to which these platforms help students transition from theoretical knowledge to practical application in real-world situations is scarce (Zhang, 2011).

The integration of these multimedia tools into the broader curriculum remains underexplored. Such as; Khan Academy, Quizlet, Socrative, Bamboozle, and among others are used for individual study or as supplementary tools, research is needed to understand how they can be incorporated effectively into the regular classroom setting. Understanding how these platforms can complement traditional teaching methods and be integrated into a cohesive curriculum would provide valuable insights (Johnson & Johnson, 2014).

There is a lack of research on teacher preparedness in using these platforms effectively. While many teachers may be familiar with one or two of these platforms, the integration of multiple multimedia tools into the curriculum requires training and ongoing professional development. Research on how teachers can effectively incorporate Khan Academy, Quizlet, Socrative, and Bamboozle into their teaching strategies, and how they can be trained to utilize these tools to maximize student engagement and achievement, is essential (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

Methodology

Grade 10-Aristotle and Grade 10-Becquerel, from the Municipality of Maasim, Sarangani Province. Grade 10-Aristotle was designated as the experimental group, while Grade 10- Becquerel served as the control group. The assignment of students to either group was determined through a random selection process using a drawing of lots. To ensure comparability, the inclusion criteria and matching variables were based on students' age and their weighted percentage average in Mathematics from Grade 9, as recorded in School Form 1 and School Form 10.

The researchers sought permission from the Principal of Aniceto C. Lopez Sr. National High School through a formal letter of request to conduct the study, following the ethical guidelines for educational research (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Upon receiving approval, they initiated the experiment by administering Test 1 to both the experimental and control groups, covering topics included in the Grade 10 Mathematics curriculum, consistent with the principles of experimental research in education (Gay, Mills, & Airasian, 2016). The study was conducted over a period of three months, aligning with recommended durations for instructional interventions (Slavin, 2008). Once all topics had been covered, Test 2 and Test 3 were administered to both groups to assess learning outcomes, following best practices in educational assessment (McMillan, 2015). After administering the series of tests, the researchers carefully analyzed, interpreted, and presented the data with accuracy and integrity, ensuring reliability and validity in their findings (Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2019).

Statistical Treatment

To determine the performance of the students at the start of the study, frequency, mean and percentage were used.

To determine if there is a significant difference in the initial test scores of control and experimental groups, t-test for the independent samples was used.

To determine if there is a significant difference in the Series of Test scores of the control group, Anova and Post Hoc Analysis of the Mean for dependent samples was used.

Whether or not there is a significant difference in the Series of Test scores of the experimental group, Anova and Post Hoc Analysis of the Mean for dependent samples was used.

To determine if there is a significant difference in the series of test scores of the control group and experimental group, Factorial Analysis with Repeated Measures for independent samples was also used.

Results and Discussion

Performance of Grade 10 Students in Statistics and Probability

This study determined the Grade 10 learners' performance in Statistics and Probability at the start of the study. To do this, a 40- item Test 1 was given to the learners.

As shown in Table 1, the majority of the Grade 10 learners got only scores of 9 to 16 in the Test 1 (63.3%). Their performance in Statistics and Probability is considered Poor. This is followed by 35.0% who got the scores of 17 to 24 out of the perfect score of 40. These students have Fair performance in Statistics and Probability. And it is followed by 1.7% who got the scores of 0 to 8. Their performance in Statistics and Probability is Very Poor. No learners were able to score 25 to 32 and 33 to 40 in Test 1. Hence no Grade 10 learner has Good and Very Good proficiency in Mathematics

The over-all mean gain score of the learners is 15.32, and this indicates that learners perform Poor in Statistics and Probability. It infers also that learners had lack of understanding and knowledge in the topics of finding the permutations of n objects taken r at a time, finding the combinations of n objects taken r at a time, problems involving permutations and combinations, probability of compound events, probability of independent events and conditional probability.

Table 1. *Learners' Performance in Statistics and Probability at the Start of the Study*

Learners' Performance	Frequency	Percentage	Description
33- 40	0	0%	Very Good
25- 32	0	0%	Good
17- 24	21	35.0%	Fair
9- 16	38	63.3%	Poor
0- 8	1	1.7%	Very Poor
Over- all Mean Score: 15.32 Poor			

As described by Kuehn (2011), it is expected that learners did not know the answers to all of the questions given in the initial test; however, they were expected to utilize previous knowledge to predict rational answers. This is supported by the studies of Mbugua, Kibet, and Nkonke (2012) which indicated that in daily teaching practice, a lot of factors contribute to good performance in the learning Mathematics process including learners being hard working, applying efficient learning skills, and being good at mathematical analysis. Hence, there are many reasons that the learners will have difficulties in learning Mathematics. For example, learners who have poor performance may fail in mathematical learning from not making sense of learning Math. Learners often have difficulties to concretize intellectual issues, especially when they need to construct mathematical relations and generalizations.

Difference in the Initial Test Scores of the Control Group and Experimental Group

This study also evaluated the difference in the initial test scores of the control group and experimental group. Table 2 shows the results.

The control group consisting of thirty Grade 10 learners got an initial test mean score of 15.03 out of the perfect score of 40 in Statistics and Probability. The experimental group, on the other hand, obtained an initial test mean score of 15.60 in Statistics and Probability. Using t- test, the t- value is 0.766 and p- value is 0.447. Since $p > .05$, then there is no significant difference in the initial test mean scores of the two groups.

Table 2. *Difference in the Initial Test Scores of the Control Group and the Experimental Group*

Group	Initial Test Mean	t- value	p - value	Remarks
Control Group (without multimedia)	15.03	0.766	0.447	No significant difference
Experimental Group (with multimedia)	15.60			

This result suggests that, at the outset of the study, the learners in both the control and experimental groups exhibited the same level of performance in Statistics and Probability. This finding aligns with the principles of experimental research, which emphasize the importance of establishing baseline equivalence between groups to ensure the validity of comparisons (Campbell & Stanley, 1963). Thus, there was no bias in the grouping of learners, supporting the premise that the two groups were equivalent in their initial knowledge of Statistics and Probability. This equivalence is crucial in ensuring that any observed differences in outcomes can be attributed to the experimental intervention rather than pre-existing disparities (Shadish, Cook, & Campbell, 2002).

Difference in the Series of Test Scores of the Control Group (Without Multimedia)

The control group was composed of 30 learners and was taught Statistics and Probability without using multimedia instruction. To determine if there is a significant difference in the performance of the learners in Statistics and Probability without using multimedia or in lecture method, Repeated Measures Anova and Post Hoc Analysis of the Mean was used between the series of test scores of the learners. Table 3.1 and 3.2 show the results.

Table 3.1. *Difference in the Series of Test Scores of the Control Group (without multimedia)*

Control	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F	ρ	Remarks
Between Groups	3865.622	2	1932.811	316.85	0.000	With significant difference
Within Groups	30.700	87	6.100			
Total	4396.32	89	2			

The mean scores from the series of tests Test 1, Test 2, and Test 3 showed a consistent increase. Using ANOVA, the F-value was found to be 316.854, with a ρ -value of 0.000. Since $\rho < 0.05$, there is a statistically significant difference between the test scores, indicating that the learners in the control group demonstrated measurable improvement in their understanding of Statistics and Probability through conventional instruction. This supports previous findings that, despite its limitations, traditional teaching methods can still foster learning at a fundamental level (Slavin, 2008).

Effective lectures are achieved by maintaining classroom control, emphasizing key concepts, preparing students for upcoming activities, demonstrating enthusiasm for the subject, and modeling effective communication skills (Rahman, Jumani, Akhter, Chisthi, & Ajmal, 2011). When teachers deliver lessons effectively providing clear explanations, relevant examples, and demonstrating subject mastery students can better comprehend even challenging topics in Statistics and Probability. This aligns with prior research suggesting that conventional lecture-based instruction remains a viable approach to teaching when properly executed (Ganyaupfu, 2013).

The results further indicate that students in the control group learned significantly using the conventional teaching method. However, the degree of improvement was not as substantial as that observed in the experimental group. Lecture-based instruction is widely recognized for its role in transmitting information, stimulating interest, and fostering understanding (Kaur, 2011). Additionally, it remains an essential teaching technique due to its ability to facilitate direct communication, provide explicit explanations, and actively engage learners in the instructional process (Brown & Atkins, 1988).

Table 3.2. *Post Hoc Analysis of the Means*

Dependent Variable	(I) test	(J) test	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval		Remarks
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Control	1.00	2.00	-6.033*	.638	.000	-7.30	-4.77	With Significant difference
		3.00	-15.900*	.638	.000	-17.17	-14.63	
	2.00	1.00	6.033*	.638	.000	4.77	7.30	
		3.00	-9.867*	.638	.000	-11.13	-8.60	
	3.00	1.00	15.900*	.638	.000	14.63	17.17	
		2.00	9.867*	.638	.000	8.60	11.13	

Comparing the three pairs of means, Table 3B reveals that: (i) there is a significant difference between Test 1 and Test 2, (ii) there is a significant difference between Test 1 and Test 3, and (iii) there is a significant difference between Test 2 and Test 3 in the control group. This indicates a consistent increase in mean test scores across the assessments, suggesting an improvement in students' knowledge through the lecture method.

These findings align with the cognitive learning perspective, which views learners as active information processors rather than passive recipients of knowledge (Schunk, 2012). Through engagement with structured lectures, students actively construct meaning, transforming the lecture into a dynamic learning medium. Furthermore, the lecture-discussion method has been shown to encourage students to critically engage with the content, fostering deeper understanding and increasing participation in the learning process (Bonwell & Eison, 1991). Similarly, Kaur (2011) emphasizes that effective lecture strategies, combined with student involvement, enhance learning outcomes by promoting active cognitive engagement.

Difference in the Series of Test Scores of the Experimental Group (With Multimedia)

The experimental group which consisted of 30 learners was taught Statistics and Probability with the intervention or aid of multimedia instruction. To determine if there is a significant difference in the performance of the students in Statistics and Probability using multimedia Anova and Post Hoc Analysis of the mean were used between the series of test scores of the learners. Table 4.1 and 4.2 show the results.

Table 4.1. *Difference in the Series of Test Scores of the Experimental Group (With Multimedia)*

Experimental	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F	Sig.	Remarks
Between Groups	5252.156	2	2626.078	184.180	0.000	With Significant Difference
Within Groups	1240.467	87	14.258			
Total	6492.622	89				

Comparing Test 1, Test 2 and Test 3 scores using F- value, the obtained F- value is 184.180 and the p- value is 0.000. Since $p < 0.05$, then the difference between the series of test is significant. Specifically, the mean scores of Test 1, Test 2 and Test 3 are increasing. This means that the performance of the

Grade 10 learners in Statistics and Probability improved when they were taught with the use of multimedia. This stresses the effective use of multimedia in presenting lessons (Alorani, 2012). Moreover, in order to have a more challenging, interesting, and a thought provoking activities, integration of ICT is the most effective attention catcher in the classroom setting. Hence, is highly recommended and advised. Adu and Omodara (2014) pointed out that the use of technology is more meaningful and beneficial to the learners learning, if it is properly and appropriately done by the teacher during the teaching learning process. Megatrends (2017) highlighted the advantage of using Multimedia Instruction meets the prerequisites of learners to be intelligent and responsible users of media. It engages the learners through bringing the world of media into the classroom which connects learning with “real life” and validates their media as a rich environment for learning. Multimedia inspired teaching increases the ability and proficiency of learners to communicate and broadcast their thoughts and ideas in a wide range of print and electronic media forms. It also provides the opportunity of the teacher to incorporate Multimedia in all subject areas by creating a common vocabulary that applies across all disciplines in which learners love. As a guru, you have to be resourceful and make all the possible means to make the class engaging and interesting.

Table 4.2.

Dependent Variable	(I) test	(J) test	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval		Remarks	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
						experimental	1.00		2.00
3.00	-18.700*	.975	.000	-20.64	-16.76				
2.00	1.00	8.767*	.975	.000	6.83		10.70	With Significant difference	
	3.00	-9.933*	.975	.000	-11.87		-8.00		
3.00	1.00	18.700*	.975	.000	16.76		20.64	With Significant difference	
	2.00	9.933*	.975	.000	8.00		11.87		

The Post Hoc Analysis showed that (i) there is a significant difference between Test 1 and Test 2, (ii) there is a significant difference between Test1 and Test 3, and also (iii) there is a significant difference between Test 2 and Test 3 of the experimental group. This implies that there is always an increase of test scores in every pair and that teaching with the use of multimedia is effective. The result

of the study complemented by those of Lashley, (2017) and Bintas, (2009) who in their studies also concluded computer aided instruction is more effective than lecture method in improving learner’s performance.

Thus, computer aided instruction is a possible solution to the poor performance of learners in Mathematics. The Department of Education tries to encourage teachers to use this technology for the reason that, it furnished dynamic and pro-active teaching learning process aside from the fact that it saves time for the teacher to prepare his lesson for a worthwhile output of learning (Young, 2003). Ride, Lauricella, &Wartella (2011) also emphasized that young children today live in a world of multimedia. As added by Arnsneth and Hatlevik (2012) that the integration of information communication technology (ICT) makes the teacher holds the attention of the learners to have an interactive discussion, engaging activities and make lesser burden to teacher in delivering the lesson interesting, exciting and enjoyable. The main goal of ICT is to make the learners digitally literate, for it offers a far better learning acquisition in getting the information fast, easy and convenient (Albirini, 2006, p.6).

ICT integration in class plays a crucial role considering the fact that it ignites imagination to think creatively and scientifically. They are growing up with electronic devices which serve as a culture at home, at school, at work, and in the community of technology where tools for communication, collaboration, social networking, and user-generated content have transformed the mainstream of culture. In particular, these tools have transformed teacher to use materials in the classroom with young children. The use of interactive television as a medium for multimedia-based learning is an application of the technology that will revolutionize the education system at the global context, especially in the developing world. Indeed, many educators apply multimedia technologies and computer-managed learning. The success of the technology in classroom instruction is being acknowledged as the current move within world-famous universities to embrace another form of instructional methodologies in the educational system.

Difference in the Test Scores of the Control Group and the Experimental Group

This study likewise determined which method- use of conventional way of teaching and with use of multimedia- is more effective in improving learners’ performance in Statistics and Probability. This study used Factorial Analysis with repeated measures. The improvement in the performance of the learners in Statistics and Probability in the two groups Table 5 displays the test results.

Table 5. Factorial Analysis of the Difference in the Test Scores of the Control Group and the Experimental Group using Two Factor ANOVA with replication

Summary	T1	T2	T3	Total			
Control							
Count	30	30	30	90			
Sum	451	632	928	2011			
Average	15.03	21.07	30.93	22.34			
Variance	4.033	7.444	6.823	49.397			
Summary	T1	T2	T3	Total			
Experimental							
Count	30	30	30	90			
Sum	468	731	1029	2228			
Average	15.60	24.37	34.30	24.76			
Variance	12.386	16.240	14.148	72.951			
Summary	T1		T2	T3			
Total							
Count	60		60	60			
Sum	919		1363	1957			
Average	15.32		22.72	32.62			
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit	Remarks
Experimental Group VS Control Group							
Sample(A)	261.606	1	261.606	25.7002	0.000	3.895	Significant

Columns (B)	9041.2	2	4520.6	444.105	0.000	3.048	Significant
Interaction	76.578	2	38.289	3.762	0.025	3.048	Significant
Within	1771.167	174	10.179				
Total	11150.55	179					
Variance			8.15	14.41	13.19		

The result of the Factorial Analysis showed that there is a significant difference in the test scores of the control group and experimental group (Sample A). This is shown by the F- value of 25.7002 whose p- value is 0. 000 ($p < .05$). Significantly, the experimental group obtained significantly higher mean test scores than the control group.

Figure 1. Trending of the Mean Test Scores of the Two Groups

As shown in the graph, both the Control Group and Experimental Group exhibit increasing trends in mean test scores. However, the increase in test scores of the Experimental Group is higher than that of the Control Group, indicating that the use of multimedia is more effective than traditional teaching methods (Mayer, 2009). This suggests that multimedia integration significantly contributed to the improvement in learning Statistics and Probability among students in the experimental group, compared to those in the control group who were taught using conventional methods. The higher mean test scores of the experimental group support findings that multimedia-based instruction enhances student engagement, comprehension, and overall academic performance (Najjar, 1996; Moreno & Mayer, 2007).

With this, it could be concluded that using multimedia in teaching is more effective than just using the conventional way of teaching. This supports the idea of Moreno (2007), that the use of information communication technologies is strongly encourage as an innovative, constructivist and student-centered alternative to the traditional learning approaches in many countries. This is the reason why visual materials such as text, sound, graphics, videos, slides and animation are used in all areas and especially learners are under the effect of technological tools such as television and computers (Neo & Neo, 2009).

Several studies have shown the effectiveness of using multimedia for instruction. Statistics indicates that students retain 75-90% of what they see, hear, and do (Collet and O’Neil, 2006). Findings of the study, “The Impact of Using Multimedia on Learners Academic Achievements in the College of Education at King Saud University”, showed that the achievement level of the experimental group is greater than that of the control group. Furthermore, researched of Gacal, Durmaz, Tasdelen, Hizai, Tunca, Yagni, and Demirel(2006) emphasized that most of the learners learn better through the use of technology in the class, for the reason that it ignites all the senses such as; sense of hearing, sense of seeing and sense of touching. Capitalizing the interest of the learners through the use of ICT to come up with a preferable learning outcome is greatly important not only to fast learners but also to a low performing learners in class.

Conclusions

The researchers strongly recommend that school administrators, department heads, and teachers actively consider integrating multimedia-inspired teaching strategies into the learning process as a key avenue for improving educational outcomes. Multimedia can serve as an effective intervention to enhance student motivation, engagement, and comprehension, particularly in complex subjects like Mathematics and Statistics. By incorporating multimedia into daily instruction, educators can offer a more dynamic learning experience that accommodates various learning styles and helps students grasp challenging concepts with greater ease.

To achieve this, teachers should be encouraged to utilize a variety of media formats, such as printed texts, visuals (e.g., charts,

infographics), slides, audio recordings, and videos. These tools can be strategically integrated into classroom instruction, not only to present content but also to foster interaction and collaboration among students. Multimedia has the potential to engage students more effectively by appealing to their affinity for technology and providing diverse ways of interacting with the material. For instance, visual learners may benefit from graphics and videos, while auditory learners may find audio clips and verbal explanations helpful. By diversifying the modes of delivery, teachers can meet the needs of a broader range of students and enhance their learning experiences.

Teachers should be encouraged to employ various teaching strategies and creative approaches in their lesson planning and delivery. Instead of relying solely on traditional lecture methods, teachers should incorporate interactive multimedia tools and activities that encourage student participation, critical thinking, and problem-solving. This could include incorporating educational software, interactive simulations, and online quizzes, which can make lessons more engaging and ensure that students actively participate in their learning. Creative strategies such as gamification, flipped classrooms, and collaborative projects can further enhance the impact of multimedia in the learning process.

The researchers recommend that multimedia be formally incorporated into the curriculum across various subject areas. Given the demonstrated success of multimedia-based instruction in teaching Statistics and Probability, it is essential that this approach be expanded and adopted in other subjects as well. For instance, multimedia can be used to explain abstract concepts in Science, History, and even Languages, offering students a more holistic and engaging educational experience. By making multimedia an integral part of the curriculum, schools can ensure that students are better prepared for the demands of the 21st century, where digital literacy and technological competence are essential skills.

It is suggested that teachers undergo professional development training to become proficient in using multimedia tools effectively in their teaching. By equipping teachers with the knowledge and skills to use multimedia creatively and efficiently, schools can create a more supportive and innovative teaching environment. This will not only improve student outcomes but also keep educators at the forefront of modern teaching practices.

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